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Civil Servant

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for Civil Servants engaged in advancing Open Science. **Civil Servants** are typically employed by Ministers in government departments, where they perform a wide range of administrative, regulatory, or policy-related functions. Civil Servants execute the Executive power of the State and play a critical role in ensuring that government operations run smoothly. Although the nature of civil service employment may vary by country and specific role, common positions include clerks, analysts, policy advisors, inspectors, and managers.

Civil Servants act as central figures in the execution of government policies and administration. They are responsible for implementing and upholding government regulations, ensuring that public sector bodies operate according to established frameworks and guidelines. Civil Servants also play a role in **promoting transparency and accountability**, particularly in the context of Open Science, by facilitating the appropriate access to and re-use of scientific data for public benefit. They ensure that

administrative processes are neutral, non-partisan, and aligned with ethical standards.

One important aspect of civil service employment is that it is typically non-political. Civil Servants are expected to remain **neutral and non-partisan** in their work, ensuring that public sector organizations operate fairly and effectively, free from political bias or favoritism. This neutrality allows them to carry out their duties impartially, maintaining the trust and confidence of the public.

Civil Servants create and support open access to scientific knowledge, data and research results, serving the public interest through the appropriate re-use of data produced and shared by research actions. By embedding Open Science principles into their work, Civil Servants ensure that the research data generated by various institutions is accessible and reusable, contributing to policy-making, innovation, and public benefit.

In their roles, **Civil Servants uphold Open Science values such as transparency, ethical data use, and accessibility.** They act as facilitators in connecting research outcomes with public policy, ensuring that scientific data informs government decisions and serves the public good. **Their work supports evidence-based decision-making and aligns with the mission of promoting Open Science for societal benefit.**

CIVIL SERVANT

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Civil Servant, Public Policy Advisor, Government Analyst, Administrative Officer, Policy Coordinator, Regulatory Specialist

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Good understanding of OS principles and practices, open data, open research, and open access.
 - Developing policies and guidelines that promote OS.
 - Solid understanding of OS research ethics
 - Being familiar with technology and tools used to support OS practices.
 - Managing projects related to OS.
 - Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
 - Evaluating the impact of OS practices and making recommendations for future improvement.
- Good understanding of (personal and non-personal) data management, including data storing, analysis, and sharing according to the FAIR and OS principles.
 - Good understanding of the regulatory framework (national, regional, and international) concerning intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights and trade secrets) and other non-personal data (e.g., research data and data held by Public Sector bodies). As an example, in the regional level, this may include, but not be limited to, the Open Data Directive, the Data Governance Act, and the Directives and Regulations concerning Copyrights and Trade Secrets in the EU.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Citizen Engagement
- Negotiation and diplomacy

- Innovative thinking
- Strategic and analytical skills
- Teamwork
- Adaptability to changes

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Clarify and shape OS strategy and priorities for the national and international interest
- Involve and engage the right stakeholders and partners in making recommendations or decisions on OS
- Shape strategies and plans which help put into practice OS (give a long-term direction)
- Develop the capabilities in OS of the staff
- Engage in the open research process
- Ensure compliance with ethical, legal, and regulatory criteria
- Communicate / actively promote OS
- Facilitate the engagement of different stakeholders in co-creation actions

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- Research is more transparent, accessible and reproducible.
- Collaboration and knowledge sharing within the scientific community and beyond.
- Scientific knowledge and research results are openly available, to ensure that taxpayers' money is being used effectively and efficiently, and that the benefits of research are being shared widely.
- Policies that support open access to research publications and data are implemented, encouraging researchers to make their work openly available.
- Collaboration and knowledge-sharing is facilitated between researchers, government agencies, and the public.
- Open science practices are promoted through training and education, and engaging with stakeholders to understand their needs and priorities.
- Decision-making re-uses data that has been produced and shared by research actions.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Manage research data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Participate actively in civic life](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#); [Manage time](#); [Plan](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Build networks](#); [Work in teams](#); [Show initiative](#); [Advise others](#); [Lead others](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage frustration](#); [Approach challenges positively](#); [Think innovatively](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Think analytically](#); [Solve problems](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#).

ResearchComp: [Manage research data](#); [Promote open access publishing](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Mobilise resources](#); [Creativity](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Work in teams](#); [Negotiate](#); [Promote citizen science](#); [Creativity](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Strategic thinking](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Open access publishing](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Information governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Persistent identifiers management](#); [Resource management](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data governance](#); [Information security](#).

CSCCE: [Advocacy](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Content creation and curation](#); [Content planning](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Proposal development](#); [Technical support](#); [Financial management](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Teaching and training](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Media relations](#); [Collaboration](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Outreach](#).

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